

A REVIEW ARTICLE ON PARTITION TRAUMA IN THE SHADOW LINES BY AMITAV GOSH

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Abstract

Mental health issues have always been concerning problems, especially in the 21st century, of course, mental health awareness has been taught to everyone. India is a country that has been colonized for nearly 200 years, and that seemed to be the cause of many traumatic experiences for Indians, who have been oppressed by the colonial rules. This traumatic past can be traced even during the period of partition of India, where many people turned into refugees and had to migrate to another place for their survival. Migration, horrific violence, brutality, the death of innocent people, looting, and burning happened during the partition process. The intersection between the two countries exacerbated the conflict rather than bringing the anticipated peace and freedom. Many years after the partition, still, the people of the two countries are striving to heal the scars, and also the pain caused by heinous historical events. This paper will look into the definition of trauma, and how to partition trauma into affecting people. The review paper will refer to the articles that talk about the trauma affected by partition from The Shadow Lines of Amitav Gosh.

Keywords: Partition, Trauma, Migration, Violence, Freedom.

INTRODUCTION

Psychological trauma has always been used by many people under different context which made it lose its original meaning of the term. Trauma is frequently used to describe both unpleasant occurrences that cause suffering as well as just the suffering itself. Trauma is a term that is used only to the event which is traumatic and not to the response, and so, trauma needs to be used for the problems which are mentally pressurising a person.

“The direct personal experience of an event that involves actual or threatened death or serious injury, or other threat to one’s physical integrity; or witnessing an event that involves death, injury, or a threat to the physical integrity of another person; or learning about unexpected or violent death, serious harm, or threat of death or injury experienced by a family member or other close associate. The person’s response to the event must involve intense fear, helplessness, or horror (or in children, the response must involve disorganized or agitated behaviour)” (Briere, 2006, p 3).

“When medical doctors talk of trauma, they mean the sudden and severe bodily wounds that result from physical injury, ranging from the minor cuts and bruises sustained after an accidental fall to the life-threatening lacerations and bone fractures resulting from a car crash. Behavioural health professionals more broadly define trauma as resulting from an event, series of events, or set of circumstances that is experienced by an individual as physically or emotionally harmful or life threatening and that has lasting adverse effects on the individual’s functioning and mental, physical, social, emotional, or spiritual well-being.” These types of traumatic events

are referred to as “psychological trauma” to differentiate from the other kinds of trauma which are used in other contexts. (SAMHSA, 2016)

In the 1990s, researchers started to study trauma, and they utilised Freud’s theory to develop a trauma model that posits an extreme experience that pushes the boundaries of language and even rips meaning. This model suggests that pain cannot be represented. The classic trauma model established by Cathy Caruth understands trauma as a traumatic occurrence that breaks consciousness and hinders direct language expression. Cathy Caruth’s approach emphasises the amount of misery by denoting that the distressing experiences would forever alter the psyche. Trauma is an unprocessed incident that shatters identity and is not remembered or represented in the typical way.

Hindu-majority India and Muslim-majority Pakistan are the two halves of the country that were split politically with the partition of the Indian subcontinent in 1947. Ten million people crossed the border, nearly a million people perished from disease and malnutrition, and around 75,000 women were kidnapped and raped. There was extensive rioting and carnage on the borders.

The process of partition has caused the rise in migrants and refugees from their native to an unknown place for survival. These traumatic experiences have their effects on the people for their entire life until they come out. Amitav Gosh in his novel, *The Shadow Lines*, has brought out the aspects of partition through different contexts. Sabiha has stated in her article that the novel delineates how this never-ending enmity can bring tragedy in the life of individuals and give traumatic experiences that will haunt them in the future.

“The *Shadow Lines* deals with the border studies, conflict studies, history, and political studies and also in literary studies. The significance of Partition literature lies in the fact that it moves beyond the sole political implications of Partition and focuses on its metaphoric, symbolic and pneumatic relevance. The fictive narratives of Partition offer an insight into how major national events can be remembered and re-envisioned in a personal and reflexive mode.” (Saiel, 2021, p. 39)

Homeless people who had never left their towns have questions about the difficulties and nostalgic feelings they experience when they are forced to pick one country over another and leave everything behind to go to uncharted territories. Because of this, the anguish of those who were driven from their places of worship, boarded trains in hopes of returning home, only to die in a wave of mass hysteria, and were forced to turn against their beloved neighbours in order to live is humanised in this account.

Objectives

Through this paper,

- We try to understand how trauma is defining the course of living of the people.
- To understand how partition and trauma related in the novel *Shadow lines*
- To look into the political atmosphere which leads to traumatic events.

In order to improve the study on the partition and its traumatic consequences, it is necessary to draw attention to any potential methodological issues and information gaps. Consistent with the goals of the reviewed articles, meaningful implications relevant to partition trauma of migrants and the natives will be discussed.

METHODOLOGY

This article has included works on trauma and partition where it talks about the event that are traumatic in nature. The qualitative peer reviewed articles on the trauma and partition from the novel, *The Shadow Lines* are selected for this review article. The suitable articles from 2010 to 2022 are selected to understand the latest aspects, which are discussed, so as to recognise the research gap for the future research

Review on Partition Trauma

Mohd Farhan Saiel, 2021 in "Alienated Suffering of Divide and Cross: A Study of Amitav Ghosh's *The Shadow Lines*" has expressed the idea about alienation and sufferings in-depth from the novel shadow lines. Due to the novel's reflection of the unrest and turbulence of the era and its significance in the modern world, past mixes fluidly with the present. The novel is about the history of World War II and the struggle for independence, riots, the partition, and the ensuing communal upheaval outbreak. The author of the novel delves into the anguish of alienation as well as the meaning of modern India, feeling of cross-cultural friendship. The article addresses the questions on nation and its entities through which the author shows that every character in the novel has multi-cultural aspects underlying him/her. The author tries to dismantle the idea of nation with the portrayal of the sufferings and lonely environment that the novel shows as a part of migration.

Md. Nuruzzaman, Sheikh Shareeful Islam E's, (2016) *Illuminated Lines* portrays that *The Shadow Lines* is in fact, presents the existence of clearly discernable lines at more than one level. Apart from the political lines (borders) there are lines across religion, culture, and ethnicity. On each side of the lines there exist a different truth and different reality. The lines that separate the grandmother from her ancestral home are so bright and permanent, which are the divisions of Bengal and India that made her a refugee, on the other hand, the line transforms her nationality, and constitutes her identity to another. These lines are experienced in *The Shadow Lines* as genuine lines, rather than shadows.

The division has left the narrator's grandmother with a horrific experience, a conflicted identity, and an altered nationalism. As a result of the split, Tridib was brutally murdered. All of the characters in the novel are aware that they are surrounded by a series of bright and permanent although ominous lines that they cannot wipe from their memories or from their lives. They feel driven to take a stand on one side or the other of the line. The purpose of this article is to look at the nature of these lines in *The Shadow Lines* and observe how they are blurred with time.

Illuminated Lines (article) exhibits the division and sufferings that were experienced to be separated are based on political and religious notions rather than for the sake of nation building. The feeling of patriotism is used to separate the nation, but results of division display that they are divided on the bases of politics, religion, which just led to the separation of a group of people, where they had to migrate to a different geographical area.

Sahiba Sabrin (2020) in "Partition: a path to freedom or a gateway to trauma? A study on Amitav Gosh's *The Shadow lines*" articulates that migration, violence, murder, rape, communal riots, traumatic experiences are the real consequences of partition. Millions of people were affected by partition and are still haunted by its diabolical shadows. The study intends to investigate how the long cherished hope of freedom in the form

of partition only gives way to everlasting trauma. This paper has very well explained how the freedom and hope of new life have tragically changed into a traumatic experience.

“Shadows of Partition: A Study of Amitav Ghosh’s *The Shadow Lines*” by Monishankar Mondal (2021) showed that the writer depicted the viciousness of partitions, which seemed to be vital in the construction of *The Shadow Lines*. Through the character of Tha'mma, the author of the novel maintains the idea of division as the source of societal sufferings. Novel's central idea is that borders are built to divide one country from another, and these borders are not real but only shadows. The purpose of this article is to demonstrate the negative consequences of India's division in 1971, which resulted in the declaration of East Pakistan (now Bangladesh) as an independent entity. Tha'mma's personal grief is exacerbated in the narrative by man-made boundaries or partitions, which were erected during India's partition. This paper shows identity as a barrier, perhaps, border is not a barrier in the case of partition.

“*The Shadow Lines: Interrogating the Great Divide*” by Pralayankar Kumar Singh (2020) casts doubt on the notion of a border and partition as a solution to social discontent motivated by religious or political motives. Suspicion and animosity were implanted in the hearts and minds of millions of Indians during the British Raj. In course of time, the chasm of communal discord grew, resulting in the Indo-Pak division in 1947. The partition of India was precipitated by the British Empire, the Muslim League and the Congress Party's ulterior purposes. The political leaders of the day were unable to reconcile their differences over power distribution. The growing division between Hindus and Muslims on communal concerns was blamed for partition, despite the fact that both communities had a long history of harmony dating back over thousand years. Relationships, families, lovers, and neighbours were all divided by the partition. It resulted in the breakdown of human values, as well as rootlessness and alienation.

“*Mob Lynching, Death, and Trauma in The Shadow Lines by Amitav Ghosh*” by Basumatary et.al, 2021 speaks that during the division of India and Pakistan, there were cases of mob violence and lynching. Mob lynching was used to attack members of the opposing group along communal and religious lines. A lynching is an extrajudicial killing committed by a mob. Amitav Ghosh's novel *The Shadow Lines* explores India's post-partition situation and the viciousness that ensued. The story is based on the memories and experiences of numerous characters from diverse historical periods and locations. Through characters such as Tridib, Jethamoshai, and Khalil, *The Shadow Lines* depicts the tragic incident of mob lynching that occurred along religious lines as a result of post-partition enmity that persisted even in Post-colonial periods. In a communal incident in Dhaka, they were mercilessly murdered by an irate mob. In *The Shadow Lines*, Ghosh represents the terrible effect of Tridib's death on several characters, and how it plagued them in various ways throughout the novel. This paper looked at how the novel illustrates mob lynching, and how it leads to the deaths of many characters. It shows how Tridib's death in the mob lynching incident traumatised other characters throughout the novel. The article aids in understanding the victim's and their loved ones' mental and psychological anguish.

Anney Alice Sharene 's (2020) “*Reflections of the Past in Amitav Ghosh’s Novels -The Shadow Lines and The Glass Palace*” examines rootlessness, longing , reminiscence, and isolation as diasporic occurrences in *The Shadow Lines* and *The Glass Palace*.

According to the article, the characters are relieved by the memory bank. The use of flashbacks by Ghosh serves to emphasise the protagonist's ongoing identity-search. To create a new identity, diasporic literature dismantles obstacles. With the idea and need for belonging, the search for the original root starts. It has to do with a person's feeling of place in their own hometown. Human connections, feelings, and affection cannot be separated from one another. Another component of this connection to one's hometown is "memory." An immigrant never loses sight of his roots. The recollection serves as a bridge between the present and the past. As a result, the desire for one's roots or sense of belonging is intricately entwined with nostalgia and memory. This attachment to one's home is portrayed via the prism of remembering and flashback method as belonging. Always a mirror reflecting the present is the past. The people in the *Shadow Lines* who are missing their home countries beautifully capture the illustrious memories of Calcutta and Dhaka. The agony caused by Bengal's divorce has been heavily dramatised. The historic family house acts as a solid base for enduring attachment. Grandma still considers it to be her home even after the division and longs to return there. Home thoughts are depicted as a cultural weapon of compromise for new cultural contacts in the *Glass Palace*, not just as an abstract form to be recalled. In *The Shadow Lines* home or one's belonging is shown as a source of emotion, while in *glass palace* it is used to understand new cultural aspects. Thus, home thoughts help in the formation of a new identity by creating a new space. The past is recalled as a living, breathing entity that continues to flow into the present.

Pabitra Bharali's (2012) article "Amitav Ghosh's 'The Shadow Line': Problematics of National Identity" believed that the freedom from political colonialism was a breath of fresh air for Indian writers to pen from a fresh perspective, and reflect their traditional beliefs and ideas. Salman Rushdie, Vikram Seth, Amitav Ghosh, and other Indian English post-colonial writers have freed Indian English literature from the colonial yoke by writing with vitality, a distinct voice, vigor, and a feeling of independence. Historical nationalist issues like diaspora, migration, evacuees, and colonial hegemony, as well as socioeconomic and cultural subjects like encounter of east-west, caste, and class, are of interest to these authors. The purpose of this study is to look at Amitav Ghosh's portrayal of the identity dilemma in "*The Shadow Lines*", a novel that outlines a few historic events like the Bengal freedom movement, Second World War, India's partition, and communal unrests in Bangladesh and India. In his search for identity, Ghosh challenges nationalism in this novel. Grandmother's zealous nationalism is called into question and re-examined. Traditional identity conceptions such as nation and nationalism are examined by Ghosh for the character's unreality and invalidity.

In the approach of challenging the concept of national identity. Ghosh analyses the falsehood and ineffectiveness of conventional identity conceptions like nation, nationality, and nationalism by interrogating Grandmother's ardent patriotism.

This was portrayed in three different ways.

1. Political boundaries are examined and proven to be subjective since politicians draw them that way.
2. With cruel acts degrading the brotherly relationships between the country's many races.
3. The idea of nationality, the nation as a standardised totality.

The border has been set up with the looking glass, showing identical sights of horror on both sides, and a sense of unity with people from other nations on the other.

C. Concilio, E. Adami, and A. Vescovi (2020) convey that *The Shadow Lines* was famously developed in the result of the assassination of Indira Gandhi, when Delhi was turned upside down by violent crowd who assaulted the Sikh community, killed, raped, and looted. These elements took the ambitious writer back to Dhaka, where Ghosh and his family were residing at the time, in 1964, when a mob attacked Hindus. As a result, *The Shadow Lines* became a saga set in Bengal in the 1960s, a representation of the post-independent India, about a young Bengali, and an Indian response to both as a narrator's point of view and his reminiscence, which enthralled the Indian intellectuals. Indeed, *The Shadow Lines* is the only novel by an alive author to be included in the curriculum of universities across India. This is the most widely discussed of Ghosh's books, particularly in South Asia. *The Shadow Lines* has a lot of traction in postcolonial studies, since it touches on a lot of important topics like colonial history, recollection, national identities, and the boundaries. Similarly, the book has played a vital role in defining and discussing a postcolonial geography that encounters the current cartographic order. As the variety of scholarly studies in this book illustrate, and it has been taken from the previous literary tradition that impacted current creative products.

S Sobana (2018) on "the theme of partition and national identity in Amitav Ghosh's *The Shadow Lines* describes the partition and nationalism. The purpose of this article is to examine *The Shadow Lines*", in order to depict partition and nationalism. Amitav Ghosh is one of the most important postmodernist writers. *The Shadow Lines* never appear to be divided, and separation is shown to be an expansion, a continuance, and something that cannot be split. Through lines that divide and reunite, the author knits together family and nation, one's own life and sectarian bloodshed, memory and reality, India and England, and India and Bangladesh. The novelist's attitude regarding linearity is revealed fully in "*The Shadow Lines*", which is told in a non-linear form. It is seen as a personal expedition in quest of the lost house and in search of their house that has been found. According to Sobana's article Ghosh's work succeeds in analysing the formation of identity by delving into the enigmatic black line on the map that denotes, where one branch of mankind begins and another ends. The novel goes beyond just describing the issue by offering challenges to it, notably in the imaginative power to deconstruct and transgress these formative factors. The article talks about the aspects of nationalism and border lines, but the struggle that the people have been through is not addressed.

S. Kokila (2013) discusses that the boundaries and borders are significant postcolonial concepts that express postcolonial thought. The idea of constantly ignoring or crossing boundaries and borders is the foundation of Amitav Ghosh's works. This paper scrutinises how the aspects are handled in *The Shadow Lines*, and borders drawn for political reasons have an impact on the peaceful environment. This type of division results in wars, mass murder, riots, and general discontent amidst the population, where the partition is a striking example of violence, perhaps, it is an unbiased form of trauma in borders. Ghosh emphasises the concept of unreal borders by describing the partition and riots. The rise of borders in the region has not only divided people in the region, but it has also displaced individuals from their country, resulting in a regulated identity, which makes border crossing a painful experience, as illustrated in this article. Ghosh's work *The Shadow Lines* isn't the only one that deals with borders. Amitav

Ghosh's works are clearly focused with the idea of a boundless universe. In *The Shadow Lines*, his desire for a borderless universe, and his interest in retrieving forgotten histories collide. Lyda Eleftheriou (2018) has criticised trauma theory's importance on anti-narrative strategies like paradox and fragmentation as the sole viable ways of capturing and transmitting trauma, because this proneness usually ignores alternate approaches to trauma exploration. The author uses Amitav Ghosh's "*The Shadow Lines*" as an example of how literary work that adheres to a narrative poetics recommended by trauma theory can be effective. However, in order to emphasise the necessity for additional poetics and ways of memorising, the writer focuses on the examines of two short stories by Urdu author Saadat Hasan Manto that are part of a collection titled "*Mottled Dawn: Fifty Sketches and Stories of Partition*" as well as on Canadian novelist Shauna Singh Baldwin's "*What the Body Remembers*". It is only in the embodied narratives of Manto and Baldwin are physical experience and memory shown to be intimately linked to how people and communities recall. The complex biological, historical, and social amalgam that is subjectivity is revealed to be one that wants narrative, but not necessarily through narration but also through other approaches.

"In memory and violence in Amitav Gosh's *The Shadow Lines*" by Subhendu Dutta (2018) mentions that *The Shadow Lines* by Amitav Ghosh is a beautiful work that is one of the best examples of postcolonial writing. The novel tells the story of two families from London, the Datta Chaudhari's and the Price family. It depicts a world torn apart by the tragedies and pain of separation. The presence of an anonymous narrator is another essential characteristic that adds to the intrigue of the novel. The nameless narrator weaves together the various threads of this memory novel, which follows the recollections of many characters, including the vibrant Thamma, a retired schoolteacher who is determined to reunite her family at all costs, and Tridib, who sacrifices his life to save one of his relatives. As a result, the story is also a collection of characters who find themselves displaced and yearn to return to their roots. As we read through the pages, we will come across historical events such as the Second World War. Indeed, in Dhaka and Calcutta, there was a war and communal rioting.

Through this article, Subhendu Dutta brought insights into the Hindu Muslim community violence, consequently, the incidents like raping women and burning them alive, loss of many people's lives are related to the trauma of partition.

R Malathi (2013) says that Ghosh is a Bengali Indian author, who is most recognised for his writings in the English language. He was a pioneer of English literature in India. In the panorama of modern Indian subcontinent English language authors, Amitav Ghosh occupies a rare position. Amitav Ghosh had a newfound freedom from political colonialism, which inspired him to focus on historical nationalist topics like diaspora, migration, refugees, and colonial hegemony as well as socioeconomic and cultural concerns like east-west encounter, caste, and class. The purpose of R. Malathi's thesis is to concentrate on the concept of nation in "*The Shadow Lines*," a memory novel that depicts a number of major incidents like the Bengali freedom movement, World War II, India's partition in 1947, and communal rampage in Bangladesh and India. In his search for identity, Ghosh's idea of nation was problematic in the novel. Furthermore, the narrative subverts cultural, social, and historical concepts of reality, while exposing the inconsistency of many different lines and borders, both personal and political. Despite the fact that the personal and political are inextricably linked, Nation emerges as a critical thread on the reviewer's sensitivities.

Alessia Polati mentions in her article (2021) that the novel "*The Shadow Lines*" by Amitav Ghosh explores the complexities of the concept of "home". Author's vision on how migration and homesickness intersects with the contemporary impression of a global space without borders, as well as the interconnections and interchangeability of terms like border, space, and home in Ghosh's work. The shift of the balances between core and the peripheral after the breakup of the empire of British, will be of particular interest, with some unavoidable implications for how the novel's various characters incorporate other methods of experiencing home and crossing boundaries. The grandmother of the narrator, Tha'mma for example, is a fictional depiction of an ancient understanding of frontier and geo-localization, but the narrator and Tridib are representation of a forward-thinking approach to space. In addition, the interactions between the characters provide a sense of home even in their way to cross the borders. This could lead to a fundamental shift in the traditional view of home as a sustaining milestone for human life: Ghosh exploits borders, space, and home in a never-ending circle in which each aspect impacts and completes the others. After all, Ghosh's primary concern is not how to get there but rather how to move, how to recognise convergent and divergent movements. The problem would be how to discover such occurrences and how to assign them a social and historical worth.

Ghosh blurs the lines between truth and fiction in *The Shadow Lines*, the "borders" of time and space, history and imagination, are in fact shades, and therefore the characters crossed in order to achieve their goal of finding a permanent place to abide. The story explores the complexities of man-made nations' borders by taking readers on a journey with the narrator. Ghosh's objective is to show that borders and national identities can be crossed, if Tridib's dream as a world without boundaries must come to an end with the end of his life. G. Youveniya, Sumathy K. Swamy (2022) discusses how the technological advancements have made life easier, while also complicating relationships. In the name of partition, nationalism, and borders, the essence of humanity is lost. In *The Shadow Lines*, Amitav Ghosh tries to resurrect humanism. The work depicts the futility of war, riots, violence, and partition, as well as the re-discovery of forgotten humanism buried in the shuffle of modern life. The aim of this study is to demonstrate the concept of borders and limits are figments of the imagination. In the name of nationalism and patriotism, these illusory borders obscure human vision and veil humanism. It concludes that, regardless of boundaries and borders, these illusions will vanish as brotherhood and humanism blossoms.

"The story begins in the year 1939, thirteen years before the birth of the narrator, the narrator recollecting the departure of his grand aunt Mayadebi to England for getting medical assistance for her husband with her three sons Jatin, Tridib and Robi, his only rich relatives who afforded to cross borders without any difficulty. Mayadebi's husband Shri Himangshushekhar Datta Chaudhuri was with the India Consul-General and had every opportunity to travel around as his job would demand". (Youveniya, 2020). The idea of partition and the struggle to survive is portrayed in the article with the help of the characters in the novel. "Thamma survived the trauma of partition, who by force became an immigrant of India from Dhaka. She spent her first few days in Dhaka and the next in India. After her retirement, she took up the mission of rescuing her uncle Jethamoshai, who lives in Dhaka under the care of unknown refugees from Bihar and U.P. There's only one worthwhile thing left for me to do in my life now, she said. And that is to bring the old man home."(Youveniya, 2020). According to Manoj Kumar Pathak (2017), Ghosh's vision of a borderless world and the regeneration of a nation

after the announcement of a new geographical border is represented in *The Shadow Lines*. The work under consideration is placed against the background of the division of two nations, Pakistan and India, which was followed by communal rioting and had a significant impact on the lives of the people involved. It also takes on the task of conveying the complexities of post-partition national identity. Ghosh casts doubt on the entire concept of nationalist boundaries, which fuels hatred, communalism, vengeance, and fury. The map's borders are simply shadow lines and geographical boundaries, and they cannot divide cultural, lingual, ethnic, or historical sensibilities.

Despite the fact that Calcutta and Dhaka, as represented in the novel, are two separate places following the Bengal division, the two cities remain inextricably linked. This study looked at Amitav Ghosh's concept of a borderless human world, where individuals live in harmony with no discord or heart differences. He tries to highlight the meaninglessness of borders, which are supposed to be the sources of hardship in the lives of ordinary people. The fundamental focus of the investigation in this paper is Ghosh's proclivity for challenging unreal borders. Mirnal Sarkar in the article "The Shadow Lines: Trauma of Partition" (2019) attempts to track trauma in the novel's characters' memories, as well as how those memories haunt them. Each character's memories are entwined with those of other characters. This essay aimed to demonstrate how characters struggle to come to terms with the past they are a part of, and how they struggle to break the stillness of speech. It's a historical fiction, and its historical data has been examined. It has also been demonstrated how a historical event sows the seeds of pain for future generations. In *The Shadow Lines*, history isn't just a period in the past; it's a period rife with memories of conflict and riot, which can be found in every nook and cranny. There's also a comment on what has piqued the characters' interest: conflict or riot. This investigation follows the origins of trauma in psychology, with a focus on Sigmund Freud. When the novel's themes of departure and arrival are discussed, he says that departure and its relationship to trauma proves to be quite important. Mirnal Sarkar's article's regular structure is aided by Freud's fascinating perspective on history.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this paper, the articles related to trauma, political struggle on partition from the novel *The Shadow Lines* are taken to analyse the traumatic events and struggle. The articles that are focusing on partition trauma, political and geographical structure are taken into consideration while selecting. The Table of articles with findings are followed:

In all the discussed articles, we can see that the understanding of humanity and emotions are beyond the political, socio-religious barriers. Partition is meant for freedom of the country and to conduct a peaceful environment, but in reality, it is the most crucial component, which is capable of curtailing the freedom and induces traumatic effects on people, who lived through the partition period. This partition has caused the majority of the people in the border to migrate so as to safeguard themselves from the riots and attacks. This migration to another country made them question their belongings and cultural identity. We could find the portrayal of the border that was shown in the novel, leading us to question the authenticity of the partition and the geographical borders. Most of the study on Amitav Ghosh's novel is on the vision of a world without borders, where people live in harmony without struggle or heartfelt conflicts. He seeks to demonstrate the futility of borders, which are supposed to make people's life miserable every day.

CONCLUSION

The novel shadow lines brings out the issues of partition, which leads to riots, rape, communal violence, separation, trauma by the thoughtful writings of Amitav Gosh. Separation with the elements that are implemented in the past memories are shown in the novel with the help of the characters like Thamma, Maya price etc. The partition and struggle are articulated through the novels, where we see the issues of identity, the struggle to lead a new life in a new place is portrayed in order to allow the readers to understand the issues in depth.

The above referred articles talk about partition and identity crisis by the use of flashback technique of the narrator. The main focus is on the identity issues, post-colonial problems from the perspective of refugees, who have migrated to a new place to make a better life for themselves. Trauma is discussed through the struggles that they have been through, by crossing borders, adapting to new environments and culture. The problems that arise from partition are mentioned with utmost care to understand the depth of the struggle that people from the partition period have gone through. The people's trauma in selected articles will pull any scholar to work on social issues for better habitation in society.

References

- 1) Adami, E., Concilo, C., & Vescovi, A. (n.d.). *Crossing the shadow lines: Essays on the topicality of Amitav Ghosh's ...* Retrieved July 4, 2022, from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Lucio-De-Capitani/publication/349505338_Riots_Crowds_and_the_Collective_in_Amitav_Ghosh's_Political_Imagination_From_The_Shadow_Lines_to_Gun_Island/links/6033ea4f92851c4ed58de072/Riots-Crowds-and-the-Collective-in-Amitav-Ghosh's-Political-Imagination-From-The-Shadow-Lines-to-Gun-Island.pdf
- 2) Basumatary, N., & Bhowmik, P. (n.d.). Mob Lynching, Death, and Trauma in The Shadow Lines by Amitav Ghosh. *Caraivéti*, 5(1), 214–220.
- 3) Bharali, P. (n.d.). *Amitav Ghosh's "The shadow lines": Problematics of national identity*. Retrieved July 4, 2022, from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/270831934_Amitav_Ghosh's_The_Shadow_Lines_Problematics_of_National_Identity
- 4) Caruth, C. (n.d.). *Trauma: Explorations in memory*. Johns Hopkins Univ. Press.
- 5) Dutta, S. (2018). Memory And Violence In Amitav Ghosh's The Shadow Lines. *Literary Herald*, 3(6), 187–194.
- 6) Eleftheriou, L. (n.d.). *Bodies like rivers: Seeking for a space for body memory in the discourse of trauma*. Taylor & Francis. Retrieved July 4, 2022, from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/13825577.2015.1091221?scroll=top&needAccess=true>
- 7) Klest, B., & Birrell, P. J. (2009). *principles of trauma therapy: A guide to symptoms, evaluations, and treatment*, by John Briere and Catherine Scott. *Journal of Trauma & Dissociation*, 10(1), 126–128. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15299730802492553>
- 8) Kokila, S. (n.d.). *Borders and boundaries in Amitav Ghosh's the shadow lines*. Retrieved July 4, 2022, from http://www.lifesciencesite.com/life/life1003/253_B02000life1003_1679_1687.pdf
- 9) Malathi, R. (2013). Nation As Identity In Amitav Ghosh's The Shadow Lines. *The Dawn Journal*, 2(1), 301–308.
- 10) MDPI AG - Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute. (2016). *Decolonizing Trauma Studies: Trauma and postcolonialism*.

- 11) Menschner, C., & Maul, A. (n.d.). *Key ingredients for successful trauma-informed care implementation - samhsa*. Retrieved August 5, 2022, from https://www.samhsa.gov/sites/default/files/programs_campaigns/childrens_mental_health/atc-whitepaper-040616.pdf
- 12) Mittal, S., Singh, T., & Verma, S. K. (2021). Exploring the trauma of acid attack victims: A qualitative enquiry. *Women's Studies International Forum*, 88, 102507. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wsif.2021.102507>
- 13) Mondal, M. (2021, August 15). *Shadows of partition: A study of amitav ghosh's the shadow lines*. YouTube. Retrieved July 4, 2022, from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sHGxed4GaTk>
- 14) Nittali, kirankumar. (2021, October 9). *Partition trauma and women: Unending lament in Shoba Rao's an unrestored women and other stories*. Rupkatha Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities. Retrieved July 4, 2022, from https://www.academia.edu/56875872/Partition_Trauma_and_Women_Unending_Lament_in_Shoba_Rao_s_An_Unrestored_Women_and_Other_Stories
- 15) Nuruzzaman, M. (2022, January 12). *The illuminated lines in Amitav Ghosh's the shadow lines*. Academia.edu. Retrieved July 4, 2022, from https://www.academia.edu/67850807/The_Illuminated_Lines_in_Amitav_Ghoshs_The_Shadow_Lines
- 16) Pathak, M. K. (2017). Absurdities of Borders and Frontiers of Conflict: A Study of The Shadow Lines. *International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 8(5), 187–202.
- 17) Polatti, A. (2021). «Not a coming or a going at all» Finding Home in Amitav Ghosh's The Shadow Lines.
- 18) Sabrin, S., & Publication, I. J. C. I. R. A. S. R. (2020, May 3). *Partition: A path to freedom or a gateway to trauma? A study of Amitav Ghosh's the shadow lines*. IJCIRAS. Retrieved July 4, 2022, from https://www.academia.edu/42926449/Partition_A_Path_To_Freedom_Or_A_Gateway_To_Trauma_A_Study_Of_Amitav_Ghoshs_The_Shadow_Lines
- 19) Saiel, D. M. (2021). Alienated suffering of divide and Cross: A Study of Amitav Ghosh's the shadow lines. *International Journal of English Literature and Social Sciences*, 6(6), 039–045. <https://doi.org/10.22161/ijels.66.7>
- 20) Sarkar, M. (2019, January 31). *The shadow lines: Trauma of partition*. IJRCS. Retrieved July 4, 2022, from https://www.academia.edu/38262200/The_Shadow_Lines_Trauma_of_Partition
- 21) Sharene, A. A. (2020, February 26). *Reflections of the past in Amitav Ghosh's novels -the Shadow Lines and the Glass Palace*. SSRN. Retrieved July 4, 2022, from https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3528104
- 22) Singh, D. P. (2020). The shadow lines: Interrogating The great divide. *SMART MOVES JOURNAL IJELLH*, 8(3), 10. <https://doi.org/10.24113/ijellh.v8i3.10468>
- 23) Sobana, S. (2018). The Theme Of Partition And National Identity In Amitav Ghosh's The Shadow Lines (5th ed., Vol. 3, pp. 308–311). essay.
- 24) Sobana, S. (n.d.). *The Theme Of Partition And National Identiy In Amitav Ghosh's The Shadow Lines*. Retrieved from <http://tlhjournl.com/uploads/products/41.s-sobana-article.pdf>
- 25) Wei, J. (2022). The impact of the characters' traumatic memories on their family patterns in the joy luck club. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 12(2), 388–394. <https://doi.org/10.17507/tpls.1202.23>
- 26) Youveniya, G., & Swamy, .S. K. (n.d.). *Brotherhood beyond borders a reality in*. Retrieved July 4, 2022, from <https://joell.in/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/BROTHERHOOD-BEYOND-BORDERS.pdf>